

Development of an Automated Unintended Radiated Emission (URE) Radio Frequency (RF) Measurement System

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Abstract -- The Naval Surface Warfare Center Indian Head Explosive Ordnance Disposal Technology Division (NSWC IHEODTD) was tasked with the development of an Unintended Radiated Emission (URE) system (Figure 1) for the collection of wideband radio frequency (RF) data. Test facility sharing, large data file sizes (100 GBs), and ambitious production schedules added complexity to the data acquisition assignment. The solution would require clever and efficient automatic RF techniques in hardware selection, design, and also in software development. URE is used to identify electronic systems by their RF emissions. At the start of this project in 2012, there was little literature on URE, so the IHEODTD development team had to rely on innovation. Some similarity to the field of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) provided a starting point for the project. This paper will cover the evolution of the IHEODTD URE system hardware and algorithms, motivated by the need for greater system reliability and data throughput.

Index Terms -- Unintended radiated emission, anechoic chamber, radio frequency measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

NSWC IHEODTD

NSWC IHEODTD is the field activity of the Naval Sea Systems Command (NAVSEA) that provides ordnance, energetics, and Explosive Ordnance Disposal (EOD) solutions. The division focuses on energetics research, development, testing, evaluation, in-service support, and disposal; providing warfighters solutions to detect, locate, access, identify, render safe, recover, exploit and dispose of explosive ordnance threats. The NSWC IHEODTD EOD Department (D) provides engineering and technical services to support Joint Service (Army, Navy, Marines, and Air Force) EOD requirements.

The Task

The Sensors and Diagnostic Branch (D24) was tasked with the development of a URE system for the collection of data in

the RF bands, from extremely low frequency (ELF) to ultra high frequency (UHF). D24, along with several other government agencies collected data in parallel. Confounding this sizable task, was the need to collect URE data during development; sharing equipment and facilities with other NSWC IHEODTD RF projects during the collection period; and the collection and handling of enormous amounts of data (Terabytes/test object). Efficient automatic RF techniques would be needed to handle the sizable queue of test objects (well over 100); the large amounts of data being generated; and the limited test facility time, while keeping stringent data production schedules.

Chamber Exterior

Chamber Interior

Fig. 1. Initial Prototype URE System

What Is URE

Processing of URE can assist in the identification of electronic systems by their unintentional electromagnetic radiations. For example, the common simple digital watch has a standard low frequency (LF) oscillator at 32 kHz. RF detection with a spectrum analyzer or frequency counter identifying this common oscillator would be an indication of a watch within the vicinity, even if the watch was not visible. Other common electrical products, such as radios or phones have similar URE characteristics, but with more complexity due to the increased sophistication of the circuitry (i.e., electronics containing multiple oscillators).

Approach

URE is a less documented field of RF test with few publicly available references to research. This required the

development team to establish innovative methods and unique designs of RF measurements and data acquisition. The parallels of URE to the field of EMC provided some reference and a starting point for the project. EMC equipment, such as antennas and analyzers; and procedures, such as measurement distances, could be considered for adoption into the developing NSWC IHEODTD URE system.

The overarching project specifications for this task were initiated in the Department of Defense (DoD) and followed by the civilian, industry and university team members. While some details of the data collection procedures were specifically spelled out (measurement distances, antenna positions, and data format) other details like particular hardware model numbers and software packages for the system were not specified. These design parameters were left to the decision of the data collection sites (of which Indian Head was one).

II. INITIAL DESIGN

The simplest URE setup consists of the radiating Device-Under-Test (DUT), a receive antenna, and a measurement instrument like a spectrum analyzer. IHEODTD's original prototype was not much more than this. The design can be improved by using an anechoic chamber for noise reduction, positioners for positioning consistency, and a PC for automation and data collection. The following paragraphs describe EOD's early design decisions.

Chamber

EOD had one anechoic chamber, and fortunately it was adequate in size and frequency range. It had a 24' by 12' by 12' height interior with a 30 MHz to 18 GHz operating range. The shielding effectiveness is rated at 100 dB attenuation at 18 GHz, with a 1.5 kW per meter squared power rating. It is a semi-anechoic chamber, meaning the floor was not fully ferrite tiled and covered in anechoic materials, while the walls and ceiling were. This design was ideal for development, where the constant test development changes resulted in a steady amount of activity within the chamber. A full anechoic chamber would have suffered more damage to anechoic and ferrite materials due to the more narrow walking paths.

One problem with the chamber was that it was shared by several NSWC IHEODTD projects, one which had higher priority, and used it most days of the week. This could have forced the EOD URE project to seek the use of an anechoic chamber at one of the several nearby military bases, adding logistics complexities to the project. Good cooperation between NSWC IHEODTD departments allowed the URE project to negotiate a chamber sharing arrangement with the priority group. The URE team would get several hours of test time, later in the workday (~3 to 6 p.m.), preventing the need for shift work. The URE project, being initially a development effort, could use the morning hours for needed

system development, which did not require the collection of customer data within the shielded chamber.

Two separate patch panels on different sides of the chamber allowed the projects to have independent non-interfering work areas. Chamber antennas, test stands, and anechoic material positioning within the chamber had to be negotiated. Equipment that was not shared between the projects had to be moved in and out of the chamber; which resulted in the lower-priority URE equipment having to be moved.

Spectrum Analyzer

Although the NSWC IHEODTD EOD Department had one modest anechoic chamber, it had an abundance of RF test equipment. All the major spectrum analyzer manufacturers were represented, from hand-held units to powerful lab grade models.

Due to the firm project requirement of collecting RF data in the rectangular coordinate (IQ) format, a real-time spectrum analyzer (RSA) with IQ data format (Figure 2) was selected for use. Although NSWC IHEODTD had several IQ analyzers available, we selected one for use which had the best data throughput and the lowest upgrade cost to meet the needs of the project. The large measurement bandwidth of 110 MHz and respectable dynamic range (75 dBc) was found superior to competing models on the base.

Fig. 2. RSA Display of IQ Format Data

If money was available, a faster spectrum analyzer would have been bought. Due to the large amounts of data that needed to be processed, small improvements in test speed, would result in great improvements in test schedule. The RSA used was several years old, and newer models with more memory and speed (>2x) were available. Additionally, the EOD engineers were aware of spectrum analyzers with larger measurement bandwidths and the availability of high speed memory devices like the redundant array of inexpensive disks (RAID) which could greatly improve data collection speeds (a magnitude or more). However, at the beginning of this program, funding was not available to procure those assets.

Antenna

Although NSWC IHEODTD had dozens of antennas to work with, the initial URE system utilized a broadband biological antenna. The driver in the selection decision was the coverage of project frequency range (ELF to UHF), with linear polarization. The biological was a large (~40" x 40" x 20"), but fragile (4.5 pound) antenna. Fortunately the chamber's major project could utilize this same antenna, avoiding the necessity

of daily moving the antenna in and out of the chamber. NSWC IHEODTD also had an adequate antenna stand that allowed the antenna to be located in the center of the chamber. The antenna had a frequency range of 25 to 7000 MHz, with a gain of 6 dBi and a continuous power rating of 1000 Watts.

Positioners

The test antenna had a mating wood tripod positioner that could be manually adjusted for height. Testing requirements called for vertical and horizontal measurements, so position was changed manually with the use of a bubble-level to keep the antenna straight. A hinge connection between the antenna and stand allowed height to be kept constant when antenna polarity was changed. A twin stand was used to support the DUT, which was typically a small commercial radio device. Since these DUTs were not designed for stand mounting, stability was achieved by low-tech means (tape, ties, etc.). Test requirements, treated all DUTs as a cube, and six measurement positions were required with each of the approximate cube sides of the DUT held perpendicular to the measurement antenna. Height of the two positioners were matched and kept constant to keep the antenna and DUT in the center of the chamber (~6 feet from the floor). The original measurement distance, called out by the test requirements, was 3 meters from test antenna to DUT.

Computer

The control computer was a Dell Precision M6600 laptop with an Intel Core i7-2960XM processor. The hard drive memory was 685 GB while the RAM size was 32 GB. It had a 64-bit operating system with Windows 7 Professional. It was ordered with a DVD read/write drive. The highest calculation complexity was expected to be the fast-fourier transform or FFT (Figure 3), which most modern PCs can handle. A laptop was chosen over a cheaper workstation alternative to allow for development work, away from the data collection site. Speed was important to the URE project because IQ data collection involved hours of data processing. A faster processor could shave hours off of the possibly weeks of testing required for each test item. Hard drive memory was not critical, because the memory requirements for the project were so great (Terabytes per test item) that data memory would have to be external. The RAM was maxed on the purchased PC, but that was probably excessive. That specification was driven by the potential requirements of the data acquisition and processing software, which was not positively known at the time of the PC purchase. The maximum number of ports was desirable, since instrumentation control was required and the data processing and storage system details were not yet known, but would be significant. The purchased PC came with four 2.0 USBs and a PCIe interface.

Network

The plan, from the beginning of the project, was to have computer control of the URE data collection and processing.

The engineers at NSWC IHEODTD were familiar with LAN and General Purpose Interface Bus (GPIB) as choices for network communication between equipment. The choice was made to use LAN, because it was simpler and the interface cables were readily available. (Changed from LAN to GPIB, later in the project, for reasons to be described in the ‘Hardware Improvements’ section.)

Fig. 3. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of IQ Data

Data Storage

Data storage and the speed of data collection were the driving factors of the project. Less money was spent on speed requirements to keep development costs down, which resulted in using existing equipment that was available. While the system developers could make trade-offs on speed versus equipment money spent, there was no way to reduce the large amounts of data that would be generated. Requirements called for collecting long durations (originally 120 seconds) of IQ data over a wide bandwidth (2.5 GHz), at six DUT positions, at two antenna polarizations, and multiple DUT settings (if the DUT had multiple configurations, such as channels). This resulted in data accumulations of 100’s of Gigabytes, even Terabytes, for each test item.

If the needed memory could be built into our spectrum analyzer, this solution would have provided the best data acquisition speeds. The quantity of memory required did not exist as an option for the spectrum analyzer NSWC IHEODTD was working with. Although there were spectrum analyzers with large and fast memories, one was not available for this effort.

If the memory could not be put on the spectrum analyzer, the next choice for location would be on the PC. At the time of procurement, such a PC option was not readily available. Additionally the PC budget was finite (<\$3K). Another consideration was that the collected data had to be transferred to another laboratory for further processing. If the PC or PC drive had to be copied, on or off-site, data acquisition would come to a halt, since at the beginning of the project there was a budget for only one PC.

It was decided to use common, existing hard drives. This was a slow yet inexpensive solution. Unused drives from the base were collected and utilized. Reuse of disk space would have kept the system manageable, but an early decision by EOD management to keep copies of all data acquisitions,

resulted in constant searching for hard drives. This decision turned out to be a good one, since there were several occasions where data was lost or corrupted.

The central processing center for the data collected from the DoD collection sites, periodically sent each site a blank hard drive to transfer the latest collected data. Copying Terabytes of data would take hours on the available PCs. Initially at NSWC IHEODTD, data copying was done unattended, during the overnight hours. However, shortly into the program, a second older laptop was checked out from base supply and used for this task.

Software

The project had a choice of software: either using commercially-available instrumentation control and data processing packages or using a development language such as C or Basic. DoD management leaned toward using an instrumentation package and recommended LABVIEW and MATLAB. NSWC IHEODTD bought a license for each. One of the other collection sites developed the first acquisition software program for URE data collection in MATLAB and distributed it to the other sites. Each of the other sites customized this original program for their own use, making MATLAB the primary development software package for the URE data collection project.

Prototype System

The initial prototyped system is shown in Figure 1: one PC, one RSA, one rectangular-polarized antenna, and one wooden pole to support the DUT. All testing was done in the NSWC IHEODTD Anechoic Chamber. The chamber's RF patch panels allowed for sealed chamber testing, where the receiving antenna would pass the RF data to the out-of-chamber RSA, which would store the recorded large IQ format files on an external multi-Terabyte drive. The control computer directed the RSA in MATLAB. Data requirements called for two polarities of testing (horizontal and vertical), so after testing was completed on one polarity, the antenna was manually rotated and the same test was repeated for the second polarity.

Initial Data Collection Times

Due to the large IQ times initially required (up to 120 seconds), the broad frequency band coverage (ELF to UHF) and the vast amounts of resultant data (in the hundreds of Gigabytes per test) that had to move from the analyzer to the external drive, test times took 4 to 6 hours per test depending on the speed of the hard drive. Each DUT had to be tested in six positions and two polarizations. Additionally, a background test was taken in both polarizations, where the DUT was removed from the chamber for the duration of the background test. A single DUT would take $([6 \text{ positions} + 1 \text{ background}] \times 2 \text{ polarities} \times 5 \text{ hours})$ or about 70 hours to test. These hours were multiplied by the test settings (frequency or channels) of the DUT, which were as many as three settings $(3 \times 70 = 210 \text{ hours})$. This time was multiplied by the number of duplicate items tested (same model, different serial numbers).

Typically, two of each model DUT was tested $(2 \times 210 = 420 \text{ hours})$. These long test times, coupled with the following additional requirements: a two DUT per month requirement; a 160 hour work month (with no overtime or shift-work); power outages causing test crashes which required repeating tests; periodic bumping from the chamber to make way for higher-priority projects; indicated that the prototype system would have to greatly improve to meet production.

III. DATA PROCESSING

Raw RF IQ data was captured and sent to another facility for processing. Figure 2 (right side) shows a sample RSA display of collected IQ data. Typically, IQ data was collected using a 1.25 MHz measurement bandwidth for a period of 50 seconds. For quality assurance, a small percentage (~1 to 2%) of collected IQ data files was processed at NSWC IHEODTD to verify that the data is correct. This was done using MATLAB and executing a FFT on the examined data file. Figure 3 shows an example of a frequency spectrum display created after running an IQ file through the FFT.

Fig. 4. Block Diagram of Current IHEODTD URE Measurement System [1]

IV. IMPROVING THE URE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

Figure 4 shows a block diagram of the current system with four chambers, two PCs, and four RSAs. Figure 5 is a photo of the current control console. The DUT antenna positioning system went from manual to fully-automated. Along with the hardware improvements, the software greatly improved, resulting in reduced test times. Early system test times that were longer than six hours, are now slightly below 4 hours. Software improvements now allow up to four channel-recordings simultaneously, compared to the system's original single channel. The dramatic improvements that occurred over a 1 1/2 year period, to make the NSWC IHEODTD URE system successful in its mission are detailed in this section. The RF hardware and instrument evolution are discussed along with the improving software control, automation, and processing algorithms, for greater data acquisition speed and

reliability.

Fig. 5. Current URE Control Station

Improvement Goals

The improvement goals were threefold:

- 1) Make system more reliable.

With the simple data acquisition system discussed, NSWC IHEODTD was up and running and collecting usable data within 3 month of project start. As with many prototype systems, there were many system crashes. A crash on a 5 hour test could result in the entire test being repeated, causing delays in schedule.

- 2) Make the system faster.

A single test item could take over a month to complete. The DoD customer expected multiple items a month. EOD did not have the resources to do shift work, and lost chamber time to other projects.

- 3) Keep development costs down.

The managers and engineers shared a philosophy of keeping costs down. The priority was to borrow equipment, long-term, instead of buying new. Software was developed in-house, instead of being contracted. System and software improvement ideas were shared between NSWC IHEODTD and their collection partners.

Hardware Improvements

It was found that GPIB was more reliable than LAN. During the many hours of testing on the LAN setup, system failures were encountered that appeared to be due to communication problems between the PC and RSA. Although the crashes were infrequent, they were a nuisance because a multi-hour test may have to be repeated. Switching to GPIB virtually eliminated such crashes.

The electrical power in the building where the URE data was collected was unreliable. After a heavy rain, it was common to have a power dip or even an extended outage. These power outages interrupted test collection and sometimes resulted in repeating tests. Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) were

installed on all the system equipment and power related test failures ceased to be a problem.

A second measurement channel was added to the URE system, improving reliability through redundancy. It also allowed test collection on two channels sequentially, which did not reduce test time, but allowed for longer continuous, unmanned (automated) testing. An identical antenna to our broadband antenna was bought, which allowed simultaneous collection of vertical and horizontally polarized data. The NSWC IHEODTD anechoic chamber was large enough to accommodate the large, dual antennas, side by side, while maintaining the required 6 foot test height and 3 meter test distance, for each antenna, from the DUT. Effort was saved by not having to stop testing, to reconfigure the antenna and test setup. A second RSA became available from a terminated project and our software was modified to run both spectrum analyzers at the same time.

An elevation/azimuth positioner was programmed and integrated into the URE system. To keep the electrical noise of the positioner motors from interfering with the RF testing, a double power supply and circuit card switch was designed (Figure 6) [2].

Fig. 6. Antenna Positioning System

An attachment was designed for the positioner to enable it to achieve all six required DUT test positions. Without the attachment, the positioner could only achieve five positions, requiring human intervention to move the DUT into the sixth.

With the capability of longer unmanned test times, and the higher reliability from improvements to the network and power, the URE testing could operate reliably, without personnel, through the overnight hours. This made for a productive coexistence with other NSWC IHEODTD projects, which could use the anechoic chamber during the day.

The chamber characteristics were improved under the URE project. More anechoic and ferrite materials were purchased and placed in the chamber floor areas that were missing these materials, being a semi-anechoic chamber. Just as when the above positioner noise-suppression system was installed, the chamber's interior RF environment was characterized with a

precision spectrum analyzer and the broadband antennas, to verify the reduction to the chamber's interior noise-level [3].

The URE PC had a display failure. The problem was solved by utilizing an external display until it was repaired under warranty. However, these emphasized the need to backup software and, eventually, get a second PC. Duplicate MATLAB licenses were bought for the second PC that mirrored the first PC. All in-house developed software was copied to the secondary PC. The second PC provided further software reliability and also allowed for simultaneous test collection (on one PC) and software development (on the other PC).

URE testing was extended to lower power devices. This enabled testing at closer ranges with EMC probes measuring the E and H fields. The EMC probes worked well with pre-amps, enabling the measurement of very weak component RF radiations. Smaller RF levels and smaller test distances, enabled the URE project to use smaller shield boxes that were available on the base instead of the large chamber. This freed up the large chamber, further, for sharing by other NSWC IHEODTD RF projects.

Two ~3' cubed, and two ~1' x 1' x 2' shield boxes were added to the EOD URE system, from other projects. One of the small shield boxes was placed inside one of the 3' cubed shield boxes (Figure 7), creating an extremely quiet RF test space and giving the URE system four distinct test chambers to connect to (large, 3' cubed, small, and double-shielded).

Fig. 7. Chamber within a Chamber

Two additional RSAs were made available to the URE project from completed projects. With the two PCs, multiple chambers, and four RSAs, four channels could be collected simultaneously. This meant the URE system could now measure H and V-polarities or E and H-fields on two devices simultaneously, in two distinct chambers, cutting test time in half.

Software Improvements

Several of the NSWC IHEODTD engineers became knowledgeable MATLAB programmers, continuously automating, improving and speeding up the data processing. Manual operation of the spectrum analyzer, which slowed

down tests and introduced failure points, was automated in the software, increasing reliability and data acquisition speeds. The automated processes included spectrum analyzer calibration, attenuation setting, pre-amp setting, and display setting and scaling.

One of NSWC IHEODTD's first software modifications, to the system code was extending the operation to two channels, enabling simultaneous collection of data on two antenna polarizations. It took more familiarity with the spectrum analyzers to eventually trigger both analyzers simultaneously, with one PC, to cut data collection time in half. Using this technique with two PCs and two chambers (with two DUTs) enabled the quartering of the original test time.

As mentioned, code was written to control a precise azimuth and elevation positioner, and it was integrated into the URE system. This enabled testing the DUT sequentially at each of the required six test positions, while collecting data simultaneously at two antenna polarizations, without the need for operator intervention.

Remaining Test Time algorithms were inserted into the code, with screen displays that enabled the system operator to know when to return for the next test setup. Test run time was counted in the software and displayed on screen to enable the testing of software and hardware speed improvements.

A complex algorithm was coded, as an option, to suppress spectrum analyzer screen updates, which provided a considerable data acquisition speed improvement (~25%).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper details a well-managed and engineered URE measurement development project that succeeded in developing a system that can distinguish the radiated emissions of RF devices from the background noise by using the appropriate configuration of a sensitive receiver, RF chamber, antennas and amplifiers. Following NSWC IHEODTD's example of metered expenditures, a URE development project could use this paper as a template for incrementally building a measurement system. Existing or beginning URE projects can use this paper for ideas on URE techniques and measurement automation.

REFERENCES

- [1] TECHDIV URE Measurement System Test Procedure; Friedel, J.; Burr, A.; Nguyen, V.; NSWC IHEODTD; Indian Head, Maryland; 31 July 2014.
- [2] Installation of Positioner and Solution to Noise in Anechoic Chamber; Wilhelm, L.; Nguyen, V.; Friedel, J.; Naval Surface Warfare Center Indian Head Explosive Ordnance Disposal Technology Division (NSWC IHEODTD) 30 September 2013.
- [3] Chamber Characterization after New Positioner Installed; Friedel, J.; Nguyen, V.; NAVEODTECHDIV; Indian Head, Maryland; 22 May 2013.